

CONJUGAL INFIDELITY, DIVORCE AND RE-MARRIAGE FROM CHRISTIANO-ISLAMIC POINT OF VIEW

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Abstract

Conjugal Infidelity, divorce and re-marriage are recurring themes in both Christian and Islamic scriptures. Both scriptures are replete with issues of infidelity and divorce. Deuteronomy 22:30 clearly establishes the principles of marital faithfulness. Cheating on one's spouse and sexual abuse undermine the dignity and fabrics of marriage. There are therefore sanctions against the act. Marital unchastity is not only considered as a sin in Islam it is seriously abhorred and followed with a stiff penalty. A wife or husband that is guilty of "Zina" will be given "hadd" punishment for Qadif which amounts to eighty lashes. Divorce and re-marriage are allowed in the Old Testament but forbidden in the New Testament though there are exceptional cases as taught by Paul the Apostle. Islam allows divorce and re-marriage provided they are done in accordance with the Quranic injunctions. This work therefore aims at examining conjugal infidelity, sexual exploitation, divorce and re-marriage from both Christian and Islamic points of view. Being an historical study, historical method is used in its analysis. The findings of the work however reveal that the views of the two religions in respect of conjugal infidelity or unchastity, divorce and re-marriage are almost the same.

Keywords: Divorce, Re-Marriage, Conjugal Infidelity, Dignity, Sexual Exploitation, Sexual Abuse.

INTRODUCTION

Islam and Christianity are among the most popular religions in the world. As submitted by many, these two religions possess a number of significant similarities as seen in their Holy Scriptures. The most significant similarities include: believe in monotheistic religion, the Sovereignty of God; Heaven and Hell and so on (Moniruzzaman, 2024). We shall therefore consider in this study some of the views of these religions on Conjugal infidelity, divorce and re-marriage.

The Edenic model of marriage stipulates that a man and woman are to be joined together in a permanent marital relationship (Gen. 2:24). This implies that a permanent marital relationship was established through a covenant. It is interesting therefore, to note that outside the Garden of Eden, the divine design is upheld throughout the scriptures. Since then marriage has remained a permanent covenant bond between husband and wife, traditionally solemnized with a covenant oath and being witnessed by God Himself as well as humans (Davidson, 2011).

It is quite unfortunate that the Edenic divine mandate for permanence in marriage was distorted by the practice of divorce. As popular as the concept of marriage appeared to be in the Old Testament, the surprising fact is that the Old Testament contains no legislation in which divorce is prescribed. In Malachi 2:16 for instance, it is stated that God does not support "putting

away”. As we shall see later, it can be submitted here, that though divorce is tolerated, conceded and permitted (Deut 24:1), it is never commanded, commended and approved by divine legislation.

Islam believes and teaches that before a model society can be built, maximum attention should be given to the family affairs of the believers. If the foundation of the family is strong, according to Islam, the foundation of the nation will be strong. In order to keep peace and order in the family life of Muslims, Allah has declared that men are protectors and maintainers of women (Quran 4:34). Islam only approves divorce when it becomes impossible to continue with cordial relationship with one’s spouse. Most especially when every mean to live together in peace and harmony has been exhausted.

In this study, we shall examine conjugal infidelity or marital unchastity, divorce and re-marriage as practiced in Christianity and Islam. It is our belief that this study will broaden the readers’ religious experience and facilitate different learning needs of religious leaders efficiently (Anchana, Jaitip and Na-Songkhla, 2013).

Conjugal Infidelity

Though infidelity is not explicitly referenced in the Bible, it is synonymous with terms and ideas frequently mentioned. Conjugal infidelity or unchastity refers to an act or fact of having a romantic or sexual relationship with someone other than one’s husband, wife or partner. It is also described as unfaithfulness to a moral obligation. Ava (2023) presents adultery as “a fire that consumes to destruction”. Bryan (n.d.) sees infidelity as a grievous sin in the Bible that involves betraying one’s spouse through sexual or emotional unfaithfulness.

Marriage and family are considered as the cornerstone of orthodox Jewish life. Consequently, the Jewish view of marriage hinges on Gen 2:24 where it is clearly stated that “two halves are bound together as a single entity” that is, a man and woman “become one flesh” when they marry. An average Jew considers emotional and physical intimacy an act reserved for marriage; therefore, infidelity is unacceptable and Jewish law serves as a safeguard to prevent extra-marital relationship. Being conscious of the fact that men and women have certain natural temptations, orthodox Jews put in place certain laws to prevent inappropriate behaviour, including infidelity. Prominent among the laws is the law of seclusion which prohibits men and women who are not married to one another and who are not blood relatives from being alone together in a secluded room. Orthodox Jews adhere strictly to the law of seclusion to the extent that a man and woman when alone together in a secluded place even if they are not physically intimate are considered guilty of adultery. In their desperate bit to prevent infidelity, modesty in speech, dress and overall demeanor are emphasized. They avoid dressing, speaking or behaving provocatively toward members of the opposite sex. Both men and women therefore try to present themselves in a dignified and refined manner based on the belief that modesty lowers the chance of inappropriate behaviour outside marriage and preserves sexuality within it. In an attempt to prevent marital unchastity, orthodox Jews stress gender-separate activities. For instance, men and women pray in separate areas of the synagogue. When men and women’s public interaction becomes inevitable, for example at work, the tone is formal. Colleagues, as

observed by Stuardt (2020), avoid addressing each other by their first names, touching or speaking about intimate subjects. To deal with infidelity according to Cherith (2020), one must understand what marriage is.

Though Qu'ran condemns marital infidelity, it does not pronounce any penalty but the Hadith, a separate body of literature depicting the life of Muhammad gives detailed analysis of the topic. For instance, Qu'ran 17:32 states: "And do not approach adultery; for verily it is a great sin and an evil way." Qu'ran 28:68-69 also proclaims that: "Followers of Muhammad do not commit adultery ... and whoever does this shall meet a full penalty." Qu'ran remains silent about the full penalty.

Hadith gives detailed analysis of the consequences of infidelity. The most common punishment for adultery in the Hadith is stoning to death. Evidences abound that people who committed adultery were brought before Muhammad and were stoned to death. Stuardt (2020) argued that infidelity is one of the justified reasons for killing another person and that Muhammad approved stoning to death as the punishment for it.

Sequel to the fact that Quran and Hadith do not address all issues, Sharia law has been used in some instances to address some pressing issues. If neither the Quran nor the Hadith addresses directly an issue, Sharia can address them as long as it does not contradict the body of texts. It must be stressed too that in view of its versatile nature, Sharia law can be different in different places and may not be completely attributed to Islam. However, there are definite "Hadd" punishments mentioned in the Quran and the Sunnah in respect of marital unchastity. The first punishment has to do with confining only the woman guilty of marital offences in their houses until they died. It is written:

If any of your woman are guilty of adultery, take the Evidence of four (reliable) witnesses from among you Against them and if they testify, confine them to houses Until death do claim them, or Allah ordains for them some (other) way. (Q4:15)

Quran 24:2 seems to be more explicit on the issue as it is stated therein that:

*The woman and the man guilty of adultery or fornication,
Flog each of them with a hundred stripes; let not
compassion move you in their case, in a matter prescribed
by Allah, if you believe in Allah...*

The Prophet (S.A.W.) injunction appears more severe as it states:

Take from me, accept from me, undoubtedly Allah has now shown path for them (adulterers). For unmarried persons (guilty of fornication), the punishment is one hundred lashes and an exile for one year. For married adulterers, as cited in Abdur (1990), Al-Bakhar, Kitab-al-Hudud submitted, it is one hundred lashes and stoning to death.

From the above, it can be concluded that while Quran maintains that 100 lashes be given according to the instruction of Allah, stoning to death was commanded by the Messenger of Allah. Marital unchastity is always followed by a severe punishment among the Jews. It is written in the Bible that:

*If a man be found lying with a woman married to an husband,
then they shall both of them die, both the man that lay
with the woman...
Then ye shall bring them both out unto the gate of that city
and ye shall stone them with stones that they die..... so
that thou shall put away evil from among you (Deut. 22:22-24).*

As we can see from the foregoing, the harsher legislation against conjugal infidelity might be the rationale behind different measures put in place by the orthodox Jews to prevent conjugal infidelity. As enumerated above, it is obvious that the two sister religions do not only kick against conjugal infidelity but see it as one of execrable offences and approved stoning to death as one of the penalties for it.

Divorce: A Comparative View:

As earlier established in this study, divorce is a distortion of God's mandate and as a result of this, biblical Scholars are not unanimous in their views as regard the initiator and origin of divorce. While some argued that Satan initiated it, others believed that God instituted it. Gretchen (2020) argues that God forbids all divorce. We shall start this session by first considering what divorce is.

The word: "divorce" was first mentioned in Deuteronomy 24:1-4:

- (1) *"When a man hath taken a wife and married her
and it come to past that she find no favour in his eyes, because
he hath found some uncleanness in her; then let him write
her a bill of divorcement, and give it in her hand and send
her out of his house"*
- (2) *And when she is departed out of his house, she may go and be another man's wife.*
- (3) *And if the latter husband hate her, and write her a bill of divorcement, and giveth it in her hand, and sendeth her out of his house; or if the latter husband die, which took her to be his wife;*
- (4) *Her former husband, which sent her away, may not take her again to be his wife, after that she is defiled; for that is abomination before the Lord; and thou shall not cause the land to sin, which the Lord thy God giveth thee for an inheritance.*

To have a clear understanding of the above passage, it is necessary we consider the antecedents of the people been addressed here. In the patriarchal culture, it is obvious that men or husbands had all the rights, and women occupied a subordinate position. The position of a woman in the Old Testament was one of inferiority and subjection while men's right and prerogatives can be seen everywhere and on every issue it appeared to be more pronounced in matter of divorce.

In Blue's (n.d.) submission, only the husband could initiate divorce in ancient Judaism, except under the most extreme circumstance in which a court will require him to terminate the marriage at his wife's command. As a result, he explained further, the men were taking advantage of their position of superiority to subject their wives to an unwarranted maltreatment. The husband, according to Blue (n.d.) could treat his wife in any manner he wanted to and his wife would have no recourse. If the husband no longer wanted his wife, he could simply abandon her. It is therefore probable that the divorce bill mentioned in Deut. 24:1 was put in place to protect the wife against the hard-heartedness of her husband. Setting aside a wife by the husband without a bill of divorce is described as "putting away" (Mal. 2:16). That implied that the deserted wife would be denied any marital satisfaction or privileges. As observed by Blue (n.d.), according to Jewish law, without the bill of divorce the wife could not re-marry. She could only return to her family, who would then provide for her. If she had no family or if the family was unwilling, she would be left to provide for herself. In most cases, women in that situation considered prostitution as the only option. Certificate of divorce therefore appeared to be the only way women in biblical times could be protected. It was designed to protect women from being robbed of their personhood, dignity and self-respect. On the other hand, certificate of divorce would prevent men from maltreating women as mere property to be discarded at will.

Other Pentateuchal books also made reference to divorce. Leviticus 21, for instance, describes two special prohibitions against priests marrying divorced women, while Leviticus 21:7 prohibits the High Priest. Two Pentateuchal passages mention the issue of divorced women's right. Lev. 22:12-13 states that: "if a priest's daughter is divorced and has no children, she may return to her pre-marital status in her father's house". We can infer from this that there is a clear provision for the care of the divorced woman who has no children as she could return to her pre-marital status in her father's house since she has no other means of support. The right of a divorced woman to be accountable for herself in legal affairs is also emphasized in Num. 30:9. This is definitely in contrast to a married woman, who is under the legal protection of her father or husband (Num 30:3-8).

Cognizance must however be given to the fact that divorce was prohibited under certain circumstances. As recorded in Deut 22:13-19, "if a husband slanders his wife by claiming that she had concealed from him that she was not a virgin when he married her, and the charges against her are proven false by producing the "evidence of her virginity", (i.e. the blood-spotted bed clothes or garment of the wedding night) then, be the husband is fined and she shall be his wife; he cannot divorce her all his days" (Deut. 22:19). By this provision, the newly-married bride was protected from whims and slander of her husband, a protection not afforded elsewhere even in the ancient Near East.

Another circumstance under which divorce was prohibited can also be seen in Deut 22:28-29, "when a man was caught seducing an unbetrothed or unmarried virgin, he was required to marry her as long as her father approved it, the man was not allowed to divorce her". (Exodus 22:16-17). One can readily concede that the laws as recorded in these passages were put in place to discourage pre-marital sex, protect the woman's personhood, provide for her social and financial security because broken home affects mostly the emotional and psychological state of every woman (Ying, 2021).

In the historical books, cases of abandonments are recorded. For instance, from the two narratives: Judges 14:20, 15:2 and I Sam 25:44, scholars have deduced that the practice of divorce on the grounds of abandonment was unrestrictedly permitted by God in the Old Testament times, though the relationship in question were terminated by "unbelievers" i.e. the uncircumcised Philistines and the reprobate King Saul respectively. Davidson (2011), in view of the abandonment strategy as highlighted above, unequivocally submits that "the Old Testament background material may have influenced Paul in his discussion of abandonment by an unbeliever" as recorded in I Cor. 7:15.

Some Pre-exilic latter Prophet present divorce metaphorically. In the prophetic passages of Hosea 2-3 and Jeremiah 3, we see the husband (God) making several attempts to reconcile with his wife (Israel) who was wayward and unfaithful. Ezra as one of the Post-Exilic Prophets views marriage and divorce from different perspectives. He sees the cohabitation of leading Jewish men with pagan women as illegitimate and invalid. The "putting away" of the wives as recorded in Ezra 9-10, was therefore not a real divorce procedure but a mere dissolution of invalid and illegitimate relationships.

The scenario in Mal 2:10-16 involved a Jew who "put away" the wife of his youth without any justification. He probably took the steps to marry an infidel, a pagan. This situation as observed by Davidson (2011), clearly involves a divorce, and not a dissolution of an illegitimate marriage with pagan wives as seen in Ezra 9-10. It is in view of this that made God declared that he hates "putting away" (Mal 2:16).

In the New Testament, Jesus and Paul the Apostle affirm the permanency of marriage as stated in Gen 2:24. Jews included the "exception clause" which probably refers to any form of illicit, extra marital sexual intercourse (Mt. 5 and 19). The ground for divorce as pointed out by Jesus Christ seems to be in consonance with that of Deut 24:1. The Hebrew word "erwat dabar" which is interpreted as "the nakedness of a thing" refers to adultery and other illicit extra marital relationship. Paul emphasis is on abandonment or desertion of a believer by his or her unbelieving spouse (I Cor 7:15). According to him, the state of abandonment is a situation in which a believer and an unbeliever are joined together in marriage and the unbelieving spouse chooses to separate from his or her marriage partner. Paul must have been influenced by the abandonment strategy in Judges 14:2, 15:12 and I Sam 25:44 as he advices: "if the unbelieving partner is willing to live with his or her believing mate, the believing partner must not divorce. On the other hand, if the unbelieving partner chooses to abandon the believing partner "a brother or sister is not in bondage in such cases" (I Cor 7:15).

From the foregoing, it is obvious that there is a clear difference between “putting away” and “divorce”. Putting away is an illegitimate sending away of one’s spouse without any justification. This is what God hates as recorded in Mal 2:16. Divorce is an attempt to protect the personhood of a woman. It is aimed at protecting a stigmatized woman from further abuse by her offending first husband. Re-marriage is allowed in the Bible when one partner dies. The Bible does not legislate putting away and divorce. The permanence of marriage is what the Bible upholds.

Islam teaches that a healthy family unit through marriage should always be established, this might be the reason one of the Hadiths of the Prophet says: “Marry and do not divorce; undoubtedly the throne of the Beneficent one shakes due to divorce” (Kashf-al-Khefa, cited in Abdur, 1990). Islam encourages reconciliation of marriage relationships; but where good relationship has become extremely impossible, Islam permits divorce.

In Islam, divorce is allowed when there is a breach of marriage agreement; If either of the married partners cannot conduct himself or herself well, or either of them is consistently cruel to the other. When the husband is imprisoned for life or for a long period; if he is absent and no news can be heard of him, divorce is permitted. Divorce is also initiated if the husband is maimed for life and he is unable to provide for the family. In case the husband is aggrieved in similar manner, he has the option of taking another wife (Abdur, 1990).

Divorce becomes necessary if either of the couple apostalized. Some Jurists are of the view that in the case of Apostasy, marriage is to be dissolved without a divorce. If a non-Muslim couple embrace Islam, their marriage shall continue to subsist, but if only one of them accepts Islam such a marriage is to be dissolved without a divorce (Abdur, 1990).

For a divorce to be valid in Islam, the following conditions must be satisfied: The person initiating a divorce should be sane. This implies that whosoever will initiate a divorce must be mentally balanced. Divorce given under duress, is not valid; because it is given without intention or choice. If divorce is given by an intoxicated person or an individual who is angry, it is not valid in Islam. It has also been argued that divorce pronounced when a wife is menstruating or in “afas” after childbirth, is known as a divorce of innovation and is “haram” (unlawful).

According the Abdul (1990), if the husband has divorced his wife three times, it will not be lawful for him to have relations with the wife unless she marries another husband and this marriage is consummated and she is divorced again. A triple divorce is regarded in Islam as an undesirable innovation (Bidah).

Unlike Judaism and Christianity where only the husband is permitted to initiate divorce, Islam allows women to initiate divorce under the following conditions: (i) when evidences abound that the wife is perpetually maltreated by the husband; (ii) if it is discovered that the terms of the marriage contract are not fulfilled; (iii) if the husband is insane; (iv) whenever an incurable incompetency is discovered and (v) if the husband quits the conjugal domicile without making provision for the wife (Abdul, 1990).

CONCLUSION

A critical examination of the concepts of conjugal infidelity, divorce and re-marriage in Christianity and Islam reveals that the stances of the two sister religions are almost the same except in few isolated cases. For instance, both religions frown at conjugal infidelity and recommend “stoning” as the penalty for the offence. From the study, it is also obvious that divorce is seen in both religions as a measure put in place to protect the stigmatized woman from further abuse by her offending husband. Christianity emphasizes “permanence” of marriage. Re-marriage is grudgingly tolerated and only allowed when one of the partners dies. Re-marriage after divorce most especially the wife’s re-union with the former (first) husband is considered as a taboo amongst the Jews and Christians respectively whereas it is allowed in Islam though the permanence of marriage is also emphasized.

In conclusion, the divine mandate from the Christian point of view as recorded in the Holy Bible is “whatever God has joined together let no man put asunder” (Matthew 19:6). Also, in one of the Hadiths of the Prophet it is affirmed that “the throne of the Beneficent Lord shakes due to divorce” (Kasht-al-Khafa, n.d). This therefore implies that Allah is never in support of divorce. In view of the fact that both the Holy Books are not in support of divorce, conjugal infidelity and re-marriage, leaders of these two religions should emphasize always in their teachings the permanence of marriage as upheld by God.

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